

A REVIEW ON ANTI-ACNE HERBAL SERUM

Nithyapriya Karuppusamy^{1*}, Sutha Ponnusamy², Sangameswaran Balakirshana³,
Arunkumar K.⁴, Aswini R. C.⁵, Athithevan E.⁶, Ayesha M.⁷

¹Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics. Principal and Professor, SSM College of Pharmacy, Erode -638318, TN, India.

^{2,3,4,5,6,7}The Tamil Nadu Dr. M.G.R. Medical University, Guindy, Chennai-600032, TN, India.

Article Received on 31 Dec. 2025,
Article Revised on 20 Jan. 2026,
Article Published on 01 Feb. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18427076>

*Corresponding Author

Nithyapriya Karuppusamy

Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics. Principal and Professor, SSM College of Pharmacy, Erode -638318, TN, India.

How to cite this Article: Nithyapriya Karuppusamy^{1*}, Sutha Ponnusamy², Sangameswaran Balakirshana³, Arunkumar K.⁴, Aswini R. C.⁵, Athithevan E.⁶, Ayesha M.⁷ (2026). A Review On Anti-Acne Herbal Serum. World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(3), 158-169. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Nowadays, it is widely acknowledged that herbal formulations are safer and more effective than synthetic ones. It raises the demand for herbal formulations worldwide. Preserving and safeguarding a person's appearance is the main goal of herbal cosmetics. Face serum can quickly penetrate the layers of skin. Herbal face serum is becoming more and more popular among consumers looking for skincare products that are both efficient and environmentally friendly. Serums have a rich, non-greasy composition, a high concentration of active ingredients, quick absorption, and the capacity to penetrate the skin's deeper layers. Since its popularity as a natural skincare treatment is growing. extracts from plants, These serums are made with plant extracts, essential oils, and bioactive ingredients to hydrate, revitalize, and protect the skin. Because they use fewer artificial chemicals than conventional serums, herbal alternatives reduce the risk of discomfort and adverse reactions. Herbal cosmetics are widely used and highly essential in

today's world.

KEYWORDS: Skin, Face serum, Anti-acne, plant based, natural ingredient etc.

INTRODUCTION

As the largest organ in the human body, the skin is essential for both protecting internal organs and controlling a number of physiological processes. However, it is continuously

subjected to UV radiation, dangerous microbes, and environmental pollutants, all of which can have a detrimental effect on skin health. Acne, also known as pimples, is one of the most prevalent dermatological conditions that affect both adults and adolescents. The main causes of acne are bacterial growth, especially propionic bacterium acnes, dead skin cells, and excess oil (sebum) clogging hair follicles. Synthetic antibiotics, retinoids, and chemical-based formulations are examples of conventional treatments that may cause adverse effects like dry skin, irritation, and bacterial resistance. Herbal and plant-based skincare products are becoming more popular as consumers look for safer and more environmentally friendly options. Because they are natural, have fewer side effects, and offer holistic benefits, herbal face serums have become popular substitutes. For targeted treatments like acne and pimple control, these serums are lightweight, quickly absorbing liquids that deliver concentrated active ingredients deep into the layers of the skin.

To create an effective anti-acne serum, a combination of therapeutic and botanical ingredients was chosen for the current formulation. Three herbal ingredients-marigold flower, mint, and aloe vera were used in our preparation. Marigold flowers are used to lessen signs of aging and UV radiation damage, as well as inflammation, sensitivity, and redness. Mint is used as an antibacterial, antioxidant, oil-controlling, and skin-brightening agent. Aloe vera gel is used as a moisturizer, to treat burn wounds, and to lessen acne.

ACNE

These days, adults' biggest issue is acne, which affects both men and women. An individual may suffer from one of two types of acne disorders. Such as acne vulgaris and rosacea.

Acne rosacea is an uncommon, chronic, and medically treatable skin condition, much like adult acne. Acne rosacea typically affects the middle third of the face, particularly the nose, and can cause both temporary aggravation and relief. The skin may stay clear for weeks, months, or even years before the symptoms resurface. Rosacea is characterized by redness of the face, small red pimples, and fine red lines on the skin of the face. An enormous, bulbous red nose; eye problems, including puffy, red eyelids and conjunctivitis.

Acne Rosacea

Acne vulgaris, also known as acne, is caused by alterations in the pilosebaceous units, which are skin structures made up of a hair follicle and the sebaceous gland adjacent to it.

Acne Vulgaris

Acne symptoms can be classified as mild, moderate, or severe. Non-inflammatory lesions come in two varieties: closed comedones, also known as whiteheads, and open comedones, also known as blackheads. Papules, pustules, cysts, and nodules are examples of inflammatory lesions; sebum production and bacteria in the follicular canal are the main characteristics of acne vulgaris.

HISTORY OF FACIAL SERUM

The fact that the ancestors of contemporary serums were made from horse blood, egg albumin, and cow placenta is not shocking. When whole blood is separated into its liquid and solid components after cooling, a clear, yellowish fluid known as a serum is produced.

These products were made commercially available by packaging them in oxyquinoline-preserved sterile ampoules (and later, the development of parabens). Since the early days of short product shelf life, when it was necessary to produce and consume small quantities of goods quickly before they spoiled, this practice has persisted. Exercise, hygiene, and skincare were all highly prized in the 1800s. Zinc oxide was used to lighten skin, but it often caused

allergic reactions.

Face serum types

1) Oil serum

Oil serums are the simplest type of face serum to make. It is typically made up of premium, rapidly absorbed carrier oils that have moisturizing and barrier-repairing properties. These oils also contain polyphenols, essential fatty acids, and other substances that the skin can easily absorb.

Oil Serum

2) Gel Serum

Certain areas of the face feel tighter or more elevated because gel serum gives the skin a "tightening" sensation. Because it allows the addition of water-based plant extracts, this type of serum is a water-based formulation.

Gel Serum

3) Water-based serum

Although they may or may not include gums and thickeners, water-based serums are comparable to gel-based serums. The high-performance hydrophilic plant extracts that are trapped against the skin under a cream or lotion would be applied using a water-based face serum.

Water-based Serum

4) Emulsion serum

A type of moisturizer that strengthens the skin's barrier and provides high-performance skin components is an emulsion-based face serum. It uses an emulsifier to keep two "immiscible" phases, like together and in a stable state, water and oil. High-performance active ingredients are best delivered deep into the skin's tissues by this serum.

Emulsion Serum

5) Pressed serum

In addition to the conventional balm base of butter, waxes, and oils, balm serum contains highly lipophilic active ingredients that may help the skin.

While allowing the active ingredients in the pressed serum to do their jobs, the occlusive barrier that the butter and waxes form on the skin nourishes and moisturizes it.

A balm serum can be made by combining dozens of intriguing, unique butters and waxes with thousands of lovely plant oils.

Pressed Serum

Ideal qualities of Face serum

- Relieves skin irritation
- Intense hydration.
- Fades imperfections and combats acne.
- Eliminate puffiness and dark circles.
- Its antioxidant qualities support healthy-looking skin.

Advantage

- Enhance the texture of your skin.
- Boost the elasticity of your skin.
- Nourishes and hydrates the skin.
- Reduces the number of skin pores.

Disadvantage

- People with long-term skin conditions that weaken the skin barrier, such as rosacea or eczema, may find it difficult to use serums with liquid or gel-like textures.
- Serum may irritate these individuals if it penetrates too quickly.

HERBS UTILIZED IN HERBAL ANTI-ACNE SERUM: MARIGOLD FLOWER

Synonyms

Tagetes erecta.

Biological source

The biological source of marigold is the genus tagetes.

Family

Asteraceae.

Chemical constituents

It is rich in carotenoids like lutein and zeaxanthin.

Parts used

Petals.

Uses

Soothe and heal the skin, Reduce acne inflammation and improve skin tone and hydration.

ALOE VERA

Synonyms

Aloe, Aloebardensismill, Aloelongatamurray, Aloe indicaroyale.

Biological source

Aloe is the dried juice that is extracted from the bases of the leaves of different species of aloe through incision. (Aloe spicata, Aloe barbadensis)

Family

Liliaceae.

Chemical constituents

Salicylic acid, Aloesin, AloeresinA, AloeresinE, IsoaloeresinD.

Part used

Leaves of Aloe Barbadensis.

Uses

Soothes irritated skin.

MINT

Synonyms

Pudina.

Biological source

The biological source for mint is the genus *menthe*.

Family

Lamiaceae.

Chemical constituents

Chemical constituents in mint include a variety of terpenoids and other organic compounds, with major components varying by species but often featuring menthol, menthone, menthyl acetate and 1,8-cineole.

Parts uses

Leaves.

Uses

Soothe irritated skin, reduce acne, brighten complexion and slow signs of aging.

TYPES OF METHODS FOR PREPARATION OF ANTI-ACNE SERUM

In order to create water-in-oil or oil-in-water formulations that combine oil-based and water-based ingredients, emulsification techniques are the main method used in the preparation of anti-acne serums. Among the techniques are the pre-emulsification method, which pre-mixes an emulsifier with one phase before combining with the other, and the two-phase mixing method, which combines distinct phases while stirring continuously. A straightforward technique for creating water-based serums is to combine water-soluble components like glycerin, aloe vera, and green tea extract with a base like rose water.

Methods 1: Two-Phase Mixing Method

This is a typical technique for making stable emulsions.

- 1. Prepare the aqueous phase:** In a beaker, mix water-soluble components such as rose water, cucumber juice, aloe vera juice, and herbal extracts.
- 2. Prepare the oil phase:** Combine oil-soluble components like vitamin E, emulsifiers like Tween 20 or Tween 80, and essential oils like jojoba and tea tree.
- 3. Combine the phases:** To create a homogenous mixture, gradually add the phase to the aqueous phase while continuously stirring with a magnetic stirrer.
- 4. Add final ingredients:** Stir thoroughly and add any remaining ingredients or preservatives as needed.

Method 2: Pre-Emulsification Method

This technique aids in ensuring that the emulsifier is evenly distributed prior to the final mixture.

- 1. Create the pre-emulsion:** In a beaker, thoroughly combine the emulsifier (such as Tween 80) with glycerin or other water-soluble substances.
- 2. Prepare the water phase:** Add the remaining water-based ingredients, such as rose water and herbal extract, to a different beaker.
- 3. Combine the mixtures:** Stirring constantly, gradually add the prepared water phase to the pre-emulsion mixture until homogeneity is attained.

Methods 3: Simple water-based Serum

This technique works well for making an oil-free, water-based or gel-like serum.

- 1. Combine base ingredients:** In a bowl, combine components such as rose water, lemon juice, and aloe vera gel.
- 2. Add extracts:** Any water-soluble extracts, like orange peel powder or green tea extract, should be added and thoroughly mixed in.
- 3. Mix to consistency:** Stir the mixture until it takes on the consistency of a serum.

Method 4: Solid Serum Preparation

For a solid bar-style serum that is devoid of water.

- 1. Melt the base:** In a water bath, gently heat and melt solid ingredients such as cetearyl alcohol.
- 2. Add oils and emulsifiers:** Add the cornstarch, squalane, and liquid oils and stir until well combined.
- 3. Add active ingredients:** After turning off the heat, mix in the active ingredients, such as coenzyme Q10, vitamin E, and rosehip oil.
- 4. Mold and solidify:** After pouring the mixture into a mold, chill it until it solidifies.

EVALUATION

An anti-acne serum's physical appearance (color, texture), pH, and spreadability are all evaluated through physical, chemical, and sensory evaluations. While clinical evaluation assesses how well it reduces acne lesions and how it affects skin quality, including redness, scarring, and overall appearance, stability testing is essential to guarantee its shelf life.

Sensory evaluation, also known as "feel tests," evaluates the product's feel and texture on the skin.

Physical And Chemical Evaluations

Physical appearance: Examine the serum's color and clarity visually. A stable formulation is indicated by a consistent color.

pH: To prevent irritation, the serum's pH should be close to the skin's natural pH, which is normally between 4.5 and 5.5. A pH meter is used to measure this after a sample has been diluted with distilled water.

Spreadability: This gauges the serum's ease of skin spreading. The area that a sample covers under a given weight is measured.

Viscosity: The thickness of the serum is measured using a viscometer.

Wash ability: This test establishes how easily the serum can be removed from the skin using

water.

Sensory And Effectiveness Evaluations

Feel test: After applying the serum, evaluate its texture and feel on the skin, searching for a smooth, non-sticky, and easily absorbed texture.

Stability: To make sure the formulation is chemically and physically stable over time, stability studies are carried out in accordance with guidelines such as those from the ICH.

Clinical evaluation: This entails applying the serum to participants and monitoring skin changes over a predetermined amount of time. Important metrics consist of.

- Decrease in both inflammatory and non-inflammatory acne lesions.
- Enhancement of the pores' appearance.
- Decrease in erythema and post-inflammatory hyperpigmentation (PIH and PIE).
- Variations in the patient's quality of life as determined by instruments such as the CADI score.

Additional Evaluation

Antimicrobial activity: The serum's efficacy against bacteria like *S.aureus* and *E. coli*, which are frequently linked to acne, may be tested in vitro.

Skin irritation and side effects: Ensuring the product is safe for topical application and keeping an eye out for any negative reactions, such as rash, redness, or irritation.

CONCLUSION

Herbal anti-acne serums are regarded as a good and effective way to improve the appearance of your skin. It protects the skin from damaging UV rays while also enhancing skin tone and preventing skin-related conditions. Increased blood circulation, muscle tone restoration, skin elasticity maintenance, and pore cleaning are all achieved with herbal medicine. The study found that herbal cream has no adverse effects and is very safe.

REFERENCES

1. Cho JM, Lee YH, Baek RM, Lee SW J, Effect of platelet rich plasma on ultraviolet b induced skin wrinkles in nude mice, *Plast Reconstr Aesthet Surg*, 2011; 64(2): e31-9.
2. Kaur L, Singh AP, Kaur T.A review on herbal cosmetics. *Int J Pharm Drug Anal*, 2021; 7: 196-201.
3. Kohakade S, Karodi R, Rajad S, Dange S, Jandhav V, Andhale K. Development and evaluation of herbal cosmetic serum on melisma-aging activity. *A J New Zeal Herpetol*,

- 2023; 12: 1472-83.
4. Shimpi AA, Pawars AS. A Review on Herbal Face Pack. *Research Journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacodynamics*, 2022; 14(3): 146-50.
 5. Khan, N., Ahmed, S., Sheraz, M. A., Anwar, Z., & Ahmad, I. Pharmaceutical based cosmetic serums. In *Profiles of Drug Substances, Excipients and Related Methodology*, Academic Press, 2023; 48: 167-210. doi:10.1016/bs.podrm.2022.11.006.
 6. <http://formulabotanica.com/organic-facial-serum-formulation/>
 7. Thornfeldt, C., Cosmeceuticals containing herbs: facts, fiction and future, *Dermatologic Surgery*, 2005; 5(10): 164. Doi:10.1111/j.1524-4725.2005.31734.
 8. Bharatia R, Gupta N, Upadhayay P, Tiwari SK, Gupta S, Sahni K. A Review on Cosmeceuticals. *International Journal of Pharma Professional's Research (IJPPR)*, 2024; 15(1): 128-41.
 9. Thorat PS, Bhadane HB, Wah SS, Gaikwad MS, Chhajed SS. General review on face serum. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, c2023.
 10. Kligler, B., & Chaudhary, S., peppermint oil, *American family physician*, 2007; 75(7): 1027. PMID: 17427617.
 11. Patil S., "formulation and Evaluation of Face Serum", *International Journal of Innovative Research in Teachnology*, 2022; 9(12): 1396.
 12. Cabrera C, Artacho R, Gimenez R. Beneficial effects of green tea – a review. *Journal of the American College of Nutrition*, 2006; 25(2): 79-99.
 13. Pal, R. S., Pal, Y., & Wal, P., In-house preparation and standardization of herbal face pack, *The Open Dermatology Journal*, 2017; 11(1): 72-80. doi:10.2174/1874372201711010072.
 14. Yapar, E. A., Herbal cosmetics and novel druy delivery systems, *India Journal of pharmaceutical Education and Research*, 2017; 51(3): 152-158. Doi:10.5530/ijper.51.3s.3.
 15. Bijauliya, R. K., Alok, S., Kumar, M., Chanchal, D. K., & Yadav, S., A comprehensive review on herbal cosmetics, *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Research*, 2017; 8(12): 4930-4949. Doi:10.13040/IJPSR.0975- 8232.8(12).4930-49.